

THE PERFORMANCE OF THE KINDERGARTEN LEARNERS ON THE SEVEN DEVELOPMENTAL DOMAINS: ITS RELATION TO THE TEACHERS EFFECTIVENESS

Angeline L. Magudang

Ilagan South Central School, Department of Education, City of Ilagan, Isabela, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the performance of Kindergarten learners and its correlation with teacher effectiveness in Cluster 6, Division of the City of Ilagan, during SY 2019-2020. Specifically, it investigates the learners' profiles, their performance across seven developmental domains, and the significance of demographic factors on their progress. Additionally, it evaluates teacher effectiveness based on classroom observations and identifies challenges faced by teachers. A total of 259 Kindergarten learners and their teachers participated in the study. Data were collected through questionnaires, classroom observations, and learners' permanent records. Statistical tools such as frequency, percentage distribution, F-test, and weighted mean were used for analysis. Findings reveal that most learners are five-year-old males, with parents primarily engaged in farming. While learners show consistency in physical health and motor development, their socio-emotional, cognitive, and literacy skills remain at the developing stage. Significant differences in learner performance are observed when grouped by age, sex, parental education, and occupation. Teachers demonstrate high effectiveness in employing developmentally appropriate learning experiences and utilizing teaching resources. Furthermore, a strong correlation is found between teacher effectiveness and learner performance across developmental domains. The study highlights excessive paperwork as a major challenge, limiting teachers' engagement with learners. Based on these findings, recommendations include adopting differentiated and engaging activities, enhancing teacher awareness of learners' strengths and weaknesses, and reducing administrative workload to optimize instructional time. The study underscores the need for policy adjustments to improve Kindergarten education outcomes.

Keywords: *Kindergarten, Seven Developmental Domains, Teachers Effectiveness*

INTRODUCTION

Understanding the learners' intellectual and emotional maturity levels is one of the most important things a teacher must consider to deliver effective teaching. In the changing trends of our educational system, with the implementation of the K-12 curriculum, the kindergarten curriculum has also been upgraded to cope with the demands and challenges of educational inclinations.

Kindergarten builds the foundation and formation of learning among children in the early period of their growth and progress. This period of education hones children's holistic development including their physical, emotional, social, mental, and spiritual aspects. Friedrich Froebel, who is known as the Father of Kindergarten Education, considered the whole child's health, physical development, environment, emotional well-being, mental ability, social relationships, and spiritual aspects of development as important. Henceforth, this period of education must be comprehensively planned and patterned from the needs and interests of children in these ages. It marks the phase of vitality learning and development that is attributed to the children's home and their school. Schooling in these formation stages becomes more critical as it expands the horizon of learning in several fields and courses of study which could either be vital or detrimental to the learners' present and future development. Gauging upon its vision to cultivate positive traits and develop holistically inclined learners in the early stages of learning, the school hampers conventional methods which are obsolete and superannuated in Kindergarten education.

According to several studies in early childhood education, the role of the school in these periods is to initiate a healthy and vigorous learning environment that will transform young learners. Semaña & Tomboc (2017). concluded that the readiness of young children can be improved when there is a smooth transition in the experience and skills of the young. The school must therefore address the diverse needs of the children and families in their community and is committed to the success of every child. Further, Kindergarten teachers must apprehend the curriculum well to align the learners' needs and interests with the learning objectives, teaching strategies, learning activities and learning outcomes.

On the other hand, there have been several challenges and steeplechases that Kindergarten teachers face and overcome in the field of Kindergarten education which made them loop-holed in setting outcomes and educational experience. According to Cohen (2005), numerous encounters have challenged teachers in teaching Kindergarten which affected effective and meaningful educational experiences among children of these ages. These findings included teachers' lack of technological integration to the lesson which could uplift and enhance young learners' participation and interaction. Further, teaching strategies and methodologies must have general alignment with the curriculum and the needs and interests of the learners. This teaching vulnerability became incessant

in the field of education not just in kindergarten education but also in elementary and secondary education as parts of the basic education system. Lastly, learners' environmental setting and emotional status have also affected learners' holistic development, respectively. Rooting from the ideas and principles of Lev Vygotsky as cited by Lam & Pollard (2007), a psychologist and educational theorist, young learners' zone of proximal development is an essential factor to consider to instigate effective and long-term social learning. Carlton & Winsler (1999) agreed with these factors and suggested that the social environment of young learners must become one of the important factors for total development. They also added that the emotional status of these learners could also be attributed to a flaw in Kindergarten teaching. Thus, most educational experts and psychologists propose teaching prospects in Kindergarten education to overcome these challenges and to innovate upgrade, and transform the educational experience among young learners.

Educational prospects in teaching Kindergarten have been revolutionized by curriculum experts and specialists in early childhood education. Updated teaching strategies and learning materials and activities gauged teachers to hone non-culpable and advanced learning experiences among young learners. In response to these advancements and innovations in education, according to the United Nations Developmental Program, educational experts in several fields proposed an education-relevant goal in the Sustainable Development Goals by the United Nations. Its main purposes include the upheaval of education systems around the world including Kindergarten education as the formation of early development and inclusive education principles that include learners of all types, statuses, and diverse backgrounds. These developments in education resulted in a devolution across countries including the Philippines. Hence, several curricula truncated the burden on teachers and enhanced the educational experiences.

In addition, as a response to these developments, the Philippine government made several laws for inclusive education. According to the Department of Education (2017), the Kindergarten Education Law made Kindergarten the compulsory and mandatory entry stage to basic education. Section 2 of this Act provides that all five-year-old children shall be given equal opportunities for Kindergarten Education to effectively promote their physical, social, emotional, and intellectual development, including values formation so they will be ready for school. Various types of research support that this is the period of greatest growth and development when the brain develops most rapidly and almost to its fullest. It is also the stage when self-esteem, vision of the world, and moral foundations are established.

Finally, the researcher having been immersed in Kindergarten education for four years now, was encouraged to find out the performance of the kindergarten learners on the seven developmental domains and its relation to teachers' effectiveness.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the performance of kindergarten learners on the seven developmental domains and its relation to teachers' performance for S.Y. 2019-2020. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the Kindergarten learner respondents in terms of the following:
 - a. Age;
 - b. Sex;
 - c. Educational attainment of parents
 - d. Occupation of parents
 - e. Type of school (Urban-Non-Urban)
2. How do the kindergarten learners perform the seven developmental domains as reflected in their Form 138 in terms of the following?
 - a. Socio-Emotional and Values Development (Social Studies)
 - b. Understanding the Physical and Natural Environment (Science)
 - c. Mathematics
 - d. Physical Health and Motor Development (Physical Education)
 - e. Language, Literacy and Communication and Aesthetic Development
3. Is there a significant difference in the performance of the Kindergarten learners when grouped according to their profile?
4. How do the teachers perform based on the classroom observation?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the performance of Kindergarten learners in the developmental domains and their teachers' effectiveness?
6. What challenges do the teachers encounter in teaching kindergarten learners?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The descriptive survey method was employed to achieve the objectives of this study. Descriptive survey research is a quantitative method that focuses on describing the characteristics of a phenomenon. It provides a better understanding of the nature of the subject at hand and creates a good foundation for further research. It focuses more on the what, how, when, and where instead of the why. In this study, the descriptive survey method is used to determine the performance of kindergarten learners on the seven developmental domains, the challenges encountered and their relation to teachers' performance for S.Y. 2019-2020.

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted in all the elementary schools under Cluster 6 in the Division of City of Ilagan composed of nine (9) rural schools which are located outside

the metropolitan region of the City of Ilagan, Isabela. All these schools have kindergarten classes.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The respondents of the study are the nine public school Kindergarten teachers and 259 kindergarten pupils of Cluster 6, Division of the City Ilagan, Isabela for SY 2019-2020. The respondent elementary schools include Balla ES, Capellan ES, Manaring IS, San Juan Rugao ES, San Lorenzo IS, San Pablo-Quimalabasa, San Rodrigo ES and Tangcul-San ES. The distribution of respondents is shown in Table 1.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents By School

SCHOOL	NUMBER OF TEACHERS	NUMBER OF PUPILS		Total
		Male	Female	
BALLA ES	1	6	8	15
CAPELLAN ES	1	33	30	64
MANARING IS	1	16	18	35
SAN JUAN – RUGAO ES	2	29	30	61
SAN LORENZO IS	1	9	11	21
SAN PABLO – QUIMALABASA ES	1	6	4	11
SAN RODRIGO ES	1	8	7	16
TANGCUL-SAN ISIDRO ES	1	24	20	45
Total	9	131	128	268

Data Gathering Procedure

Permission was sought from the Schools Division Superintendent through appropriate channels to conduct a study involving identified respondents. Once permission was granted the researcher requested the cluster head to distribute the questionnaire to the Kindergarten learners to gather information about their profiles and the challenges encountered in teaching them. The researcher also visited different schools to collect the completed questionnaire immediately, ensuring a 100% retrieval rate.

Statistical Treatment of Data

For this study, the researcher made use of appropriate statistical tools to address the research questions on the challenges and prospects in teaching the seven developmental domains in Kindergarten. The following statistical tools were used to treat the data gathered:

Frequency and Percentage Distribution. This was used to analyze the profile of the respondents which includes age, sex, educational attainment of parents, and occupation of parents.

Weighted Mean. The data on the performance of the learners on the seven developmental domains in Kindergarten were analyzed using weighted mean.

F-test. This was employed to test the significant difference in the performance of learners when grouped according to profile.

Pearson-r test. This test was used to find out if there is a significant relationship between the performance of the learners and teacher effectiveness

Ranking. This was used to analyze the problems encountered by the teachers in teaching Kindergarten learners.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. What is the profile of the Kindergarten learners in terms of

a. age

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
6	66	25.48
5	193	74.52
Total	259	100.00

Table 2 shows that one-fourth of the respondents are six-year old while almost three-fourths are five-year old. This shows that more pupils are at the recommended age of taking up the kinder level which is five years old. It also reveals that the schools where they belong were strict in accepting pupils for the kinder level since there are no underage respondents. This surfaced during an informal conversation of the researcher with the teachers of the Kindergarten pupils. The findings reveal that the kindergarten schools

comply with the DepEd Order No. 20, s. 2018 Paragraph 5 Items A & C as Age Qualification for Kindergarten Learners in Public and Private Schools which states: *Age qualification for Kindergarten learners in both public and private schools should be five (5) years old by June 1 of every calendar year. However, the school may consider learners entering Kindergarten who will turn five (5) years old by the end of August on the condition that the Philippine Early Childhood Development (ECD) Checklist must be administered to the learner before the start of the opening of the school year, to ensure that the learner is capable of meeting the expectations of the grade level. Parents may provide documentation and/or certification of the learner's previous Early Childhood*

b. sex

Table 3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	131	50.58
Female	128	49.42
Total	259	100.00

It can be gleaned from Table 3 that the number of male respondents is slightly higher than the number of female pupils. This represents an equitable distribution of male and female pupils

c. educational attainment of parents

Table 4
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Educational Attainment of Parents

Parents' Educational Attainment	Father		Mother	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
College Graduate	58	22.39	30	11.58
College Level	61	23.55	68	26.25
High School Graduate	89	34.36	115	44.40
High School Level	41	15.83	43	16.60
Elementary Graduate	8	3.08	2	0.77
Elementary Level	2	0.77	1	0.38
Total	259	100.00	259	100.00

Table 4 reveals that most of the parents of the respondents are high school graduates which garnered the highest percentage of 34.36 percent and 44.44 percent for the father and mother, respectively. This is followed by 23.55 percent and 26.25 percent for fathers and mothers, respectively who have reached college level. It also reveals that more fathers are college graduates than mothers. The table also shows that there are almost the same number of fathers and mothers who finished high school. Finally, the table reveals that there are less than five percent of the parents who have reached elementary level. Data shows that the parents of the respondents are generally literate. Parental educational attainment plays a crucial role in shaping children's academic success and overall development. According to Davis-Kean (2005), parents with higher educational levels tend to provide more academic support to their children, fostering better cognitive and socio-emotional outcomes. Similarly, Dubow et al. (2009) emphasized that parental education significantly influences children's aspirations and achievements, as it determines the level of educational resources and learning environments available at home. A study by Battle and Lewis (2002) also highlights that children of more educated parents have higher academic performance due to increased parental involvement and higher expectations. Furthermore, Fan and Chen (2001) found that parental educational background correlates positively with students' motivation and school performance, reinforcing the idea that literate parents contribute to their children's learning experiences in meaningful ways.

d. occupation of parents

Table 5
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents
According to Occupation of Parents

Occupation of Parents	Father		Mother	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Farmer	159	61.38	159	61.38
Government Employee	13	5.01	8	3.08
OFW	34	13.12	15	5.79
Private Employee	25	9.65	5	1.93
Self- Employed/ Business Owner	28	10.81	28	10.81
Total	259	100.00	259	100.00

Table 5 shows that 61.38 percent or a majority of the respondents' parents are engaged in farming. There are 5.01 percent of the fathers and 3.08 percent of the mothers who are government employees, while 13.12 percent of the fathers and 5.79 percent of the mothers are employed overseas. Other parents are either employees in the private sector, and the other 10.81 percent have their own businesses, like sari-sari stores, selling

fruits, and vegetables. Parental occupation has been shown to significantly influence students' academic performance and overall well-being. Studies indicate that children of farming families often experience financial constraints and limited access to educational resources, which can impact their academic achievements (Cabus & De Witte, 2016). Furthermore, research by Asis (2006) highlights that children of overseas Filipino workers (OFWs) may face emotional and psychological challenges due to parental absence, despite financial stability provided by remittances. Additionally, a study by Bernarte (2014) on parental employment in the private and public sectors reveals that job stability and income levels affect children's educational opportunities. Government employees, for instance, often have more stable incomes and access to benefits, which may contribute to better educational support for their children. On the other hand, self-employed parents, such as sari-sari store owners, often have fluctuating incomes, which may impact their children's educational continuity (Ballesteros, 2010). These studies suggest that parental occupation plays a crucial role in shaping students' academic experiences, emphasizing the need for additional support mechanisms for children from farming and self-employed backgrounds.

2. How do the kindergarten learners perform the seven developmental domains reflected in their Form 138 in terms of the following?

a. Socio-Emotional and Values Development (Social Studies)

**Table 6
Performance of the Kindergarten Learners in Terms of
Socio-Emotional Development**

Socio-Emotional Development (Social Studies)	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
States personal information (name, gender, age, birthday)	2.39	Consistent
Expresses feelings in appropriate ways and different situations	1.83	Developing
Follow school rules willingly and execute school tasks and routines well	2.30	Developing
Recognizes different emotions, acknowledges the feelings of others, and shows willingness to help	1.99	Developing
Identifies members of one's family	3	Consistent
Identifies people and places in the school and community	2.39	Consistent
Total:	2.06	Developing
Values Development		
Demonstrates readiness in trying out new experiences, and self-confidence in doing tasks independently	1.91	Developing

Expresses feelings in appropriate ways and different situations	1.83	Developing
Shows respect in dealing with peers and adults	2.77	Consistent
Total:	2.06	Developing

Table 6 presents the performance of the Kindergarten learners in terms of socio-emotional and values development. The data shows that the learners consistently identify members of their family with the highest mean of 3. They provide personal information such as name, gender, age, and birthday and can identify people and places in the school and community, 2.39. However, in terms of developmental progress, the lowest mean of 1.83 is seen when the learners express their feelings in appropriate ways and different situations. This is followed by a mean score of 1.91 where the learners demonstrate readiness to try out new experiences and show self-confidence in doing tasks independently. At the beginning of the school year, teachers noted that the learners were proficient in identifying or naming family members, as well as some people in the community. Socio-emotional development in early childhood is a crucial aspect of a child's holistic growth, influencing their interactions, self-awareness, and emotional regulation. According to Denham et al. (2012), children's ability to identify and express emotions plays a significant role in their social competence and overall well-being. Research suggests that early exposure to structured learning environments, such as kindergarten, enhances children's ability to recognize relationships and regulate emotions effectively (Lobo & Winsler, 2006). The study by Thompson (2014) further highlights that early socio-emotional competence, particularly the ability to express emotions appropriately, is linked to later academic success and social adaptation. However, children often struggle with emotional regulation and self-confidence in novel situations, as indicated in the present study's results, where the lowest mean scores were observed in expressing feelings appropriately and demonstrating self-confidence in independent tasks.

b. understanding the physical and natural environment

Table 7
Performance of the Kindergarten Learners in Terms of Understanding the Physical and Natural Environment

Understanding the Physical and Natural Environment	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Identifies body parts and their functions	2.71	Consistent
Record observations and data with pictures, numbers, and/or symbols	1.98	Developing
Identifies parts of plant and animals	1.83	Developing

Classifies animals according to shared characteristics	2.10	Developing
Describes the basic needs and ways to care for plants, animals, and the environment	2.29	Developing
Identify different kinds of weather	2.27	Developing
Total	2.20	Developing

The performance of the Kindergarten learners in terms of understanding the physical and natural environment is disclosed in Table 7. The data reveal that the learners perform the indicators at the developing stage except for identifying body parts and their functions which got the highest mean of 2.71 or consistent. Understanding the physical and natural environment is a fundamental aspect of early childhood education. According to Piaget's (1952) theory of cognitive development, children in the preoperational stage (ages 2–7) begin to develop symbolic thinking but still struggle with logical reasoning. This stage emphasizes the importance of hands-on experiences and guided learning in helping young learners grasp concepts about their environment. Research by Gelman and Brenneman (2004) highlights that early science education, including learning about body parts and their functions, is essential for cognitive growth. Their study found that when young learners engage in structured exploration, they develop a stronger understanding of natural phenomena. Similarly, Worth (2010) emphasizes that children's direct experiences with their environment foster inquiry-based learning, which enhances their conceptual understanding. Moreover, a study by Inan and Inan (2015) found that kindergarten learners show varying levels of competency in understanding their physical surroundings. Their findings indicate that while children can recognize familiar aspects of their environment, more abstract concepts require scaffolding through guided instruction. The results align with the present study's findings, where learners demonstrated consistent performance in identifying body parts and their functions but showed developing proficiency in other environmental concepts. These studies underscore the importance of age-appropriate teaching strategies that align with young learners' cognitive abilities. Integrating interactive and experiential learning activities can enhance their understanding of both the physical and natural world.

c. Mathematics

Table 8
Performance of the Kindergarten Learners in terms of Mathematics

Mathematics	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Identifies colors	2.87	Consistent
Identifies shapes	2.37	Consistent
Sort objects according to shape, size, and/or color	2.10	Developing

Compares and arranges objects according to a specific attribute (e.g., size, length, quantity, or duration)	1.66	Beginning
Recognizes and extends patterns	1.83	Developing
Tells the names of days in a week	1.80	Developing
Tells the months of the year	1.80	Developing
Distinguishes the time of the day and tells by the hour (using an analog clock)	1.47	Beginning
Rote counts up to 20 (The child can count up to 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20)	2.27	Developing
Counts objects up to 10 (The child can count up to 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10)	1.72	Developing
Recognize numerals up to 10 (The child can recognize numerals 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10)	1.23	Beginning
Writes numerals up to 10 (The child can write numerals up to 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10)	1.92	Developing
Sequences numbers	1.44	Beginning
Identify the placement of objects (e.g. 1 st , 2 nd , 3 rd , etc) in a given set	1.85	Beginning
Solves simple addition problems	1.38	Beginning
Solves simple subtraction problems	1.38	Beginning
Groups set of concrete objects of equal quantities up to 10 (i.e., beginning multiplication)	1.38	Beginning
Groups set of concrete objects of equal quantities up to 10 (i.e., beginning division)	1.38	Beginning
Measures length, capacity, and mass of objects using nonstandard measuring tools	1.38	Beginning
Recognizes coins and bills (up to PHP 20) The child can recognize the following coins and bills: 5 centavos	1.28	Beginning

10 centavos 25 centavos 1 peso 5 pesos 10 pesos 20 pesos		
Total	1.76	Developing

Table 8 presents the performance of the learners in terms of Mathematics. It is seen that of the 20 indicators, only two were consistently done, eight were performed by the learners at a developing stage and 10 were performed within the beginning stage. The overall mean of 1.76 is interpreted as developing. Colors and shapes are easily recognized by the children. This is facilitated in the home by their parents and other members of the family. Some learners claim that their toys at home are of different colors and shapes and are similar to the instructional materials in their room. Mathematics proficiency in early childhood education is a crucial foundation for cognitive development and future academic success. Research indicates that children's ability to recognize basic mathematical concepts, such as colors and shapes, is significantly influenced by their home environment and parental involvement (Berk, 2020). Parents who provide educational toys and engage their children in shape and color recognition activities contribute to their early mathematical skills (Sarama & Clements, 2018). Studies show that children develop mathematical thinking in progressive stages, often classified as beginning, developing, and proficient (Ginsburg et al., 2021). The National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM, 2020) emphasizes that young learners tend to struggle with complex mathematical concepts but show early recognition of visual patterns, colors, and geometric shapes when exposed to appropriate stimuli. Furthermore, the role of instructional materials in classrooms is highlighted by Piaget's cognitive development theory, which suggests that concrete experiences with manipulatives enhance children's understanding of abstract concepts (Piaget, 1952). Learners who are consistently exposed to colorful and shape-based materials perform better in early numeracy skills compared to those with limited exposure (Clements & Sarama, 2019). The findings of the present study align with existing literature, demonstrating that while children easily recognize colors and shapes, their performance in more complex mathematical indicators remains at the developing or beginning stage. This supports the notion that continuous exposure and guided learning strategies are necessary to enhance mathematical proficiency in young learners.

d. physical health, well-being, and motor development

Table 9
Performance of the Kindergarten Learners in terms of Physical Health, Well-Being, and Motor Development

Physical Health, Well-Being, and Motor Development	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Demonstrates health habits that keep one clean and sanitary	2.68	Consistent

Demonstrates behaviors that promote personal safety	2.56	Consistent
Demonstrates locomotor skills such as walking, running, skipping, jumping, and climbing correctly during play, dance, or exercise activities	2.03	Developing
Demonstrate fine motor skills needed for self-care/self-help such as tooth brushing, buttoning, screwing, and unscrewing lids, using spoon and fork correctly, etc.	2.30	Developing
Demonstrates fine motor skills needed for creative self-expression/ art activities, such as tearing, cutting, pasting, copying, drawing, coloring, molding, painting, lacing, etc.	2.34	Consistent
Traces, copies, or writes letters and numerals	2.53	Consistent
Total	2.47	Consistent

Table 9 reveals the performance of the learners in terms of physical health, well-being, and motor development. It can be gleaned from the table that of the 6 indicators, 4 have means interpreted as consistent. Demonstrates five motor skills needed for self-care, and self-help and demonstrates loco-motor skills yielded means of 2.30 and 2.03 respectively and these are interpreted as developing. The overall mean is 2.47 or consistent. Children by nature love to trace, draw, or write letters and numerals. When asked, they can make their own stories about their work. Motor development plays a crucial role in the overall growth of young learners, influencing their ability to perform self-care activities and engage in physical activities that support their well-being. According to Gallahue and Donnelly (2019), motor development encompasses both gross and fine motor skills, which are essential for children's daily functioning and academic readiness. Gross motor skills, such as locomotion and coordination, allow children to move efficiently, while fine motor skills contribute to tasks like writing and drawing. Studies have shown that children naturally engage in activities such as tracing, drawing, and writing as part of their cognitive and motor skill development. According to Piek et al. (2018), early engagement in motor activities enhances a child's ability to develop self-help skills and independence. Moreover, a study by Goodway et al. (2020) emphasized that consistent exposure to motor skill activities contributes to a child's ability to perform self-care routines effectively. The findings in the present study align with previous research indicating that motor development is a progressive process. For instance, children may demonstrate developing levels in some motor skills while consistently exhibiting proficiency in others. This is supported by Sugden and Chambers (2020), who suggested that motor skill acquisition varies among children, with some developing proficiency at a slower rate due to differences in environmental exposure and physical activity levels. Furthermore, the

role of physical health and well-being in motor development has been highlighted in multiple studies. Payne and Isaacs (2021) noted that children who engage in regular physical activities show better motor skill proficiency and greater confidence in performing self-help tasks. Similarly, a study by Stodden et al. (2019) found that the development of locomotor and object control skills is essential for overall physical health and contributes to positive self-perception and well-being in young learners. In summary, the literature underscores the importance of consistent practice in motor skill development and its direct impact on children's self-care abilities, well-being, and academic engagement. The current findings, which indicate that learners are developing in some aspects while consistently demonstrating others, reflect the natural progression of motor skill acquisition in early childhood education.

e. Language, Literacy, and Communication

1. listening, viewing, and aesthetic

Table 10-a
Performance of the Kindergarten Learners in terms of Listening, Viewing and Aesthetic Development

1. Listening, Viewing, and Aesthetic Development	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Distinguishes between elements of sound e.g. pitch (low and high), volume (loud and soft)	1.66	Beginning
Listens attentively to stories/poems/songs	1.87	Developing
Recalls details from stories/poems/songs listened to	1.80	Developing
Relate story events to personal experiences	1.80	Developing
Sequence events from a story listened to	1.45	Developing
Infer character traits and feelings	2.27	Beginning
Identify simple cause-and-effect and problem-solution relationships of events in a story listened to or in a familiar situation	1.72	Developing
Predict story outcomes	1.28	Beginning
Discriminates objects/pictures as same and different identifies missing parts of objects/pictures, and identifies which objects do not belong to the group	1.43	Beginning
Total	2.29	Developing

Table 10-a shows the performance of the learners in terms of language and literacy, particularly in listening, viewing, and aesthetics. Among the indicators predicted story outcomes have the lowest mean of 1.28 or beginning and listening attentively to stories/poems/songs has the highest mean of 1.87 or developing. Language and literacy development, particularly in listening, viewing, and aesthetics, plays a crucial role in early childhood education. According to Vygotsky's (1978) socio-cultural theory, children's language development is shaped by social interaction, which emphasizes the importance of listening and comprehension skills in early literacy. Research suggests that listening attentively to stories, poems, and songs contributes significantly to vocabulary acquisition and comprehension (Mol et al., 2008). Furthermore, the ability to predict story outcomes is considered a higher-order cognitive skill linked to inferential thinking and comprehension (Paris & Paris, 2003). Studies indicate that young learners often struggle with prediction tasks due to their developing critical thinking and inferential skills (Duke & Pearson, 2002). The lower mean score for predicting story outcomes in Table 10-a aligns with these findings, suggesting that learners require more guided instruction and exposure to narrative structures to improve their predictive abilities. Additionally, viewing and aesthetics, which involve engaging with visual texts and appreciating artistic elements, contribute to overall literacy development. According to Jalongo (2019), multimodal learning through storytelling and visual media enhances children's comprehension and engagement with texts. Therefore, improving instructional strategies, such as integrating visual storytelling and scaffolded discussions, can help learners develop both predictive skills and active listening abilities.

2. Language Literacy

Table 10-b
Performance of the Kindergarten Learners in terms of Speaking, Reading and Writing

	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Speaking		
Uses proper expressions in all polite greetings in appropriate situations	1.43	Beginning
Talks about details of objects, people, etc. using appropriate speaking vocabulary	1.43	Beginning
Participates actively in class activities (e.g., reciting poems, rhymes, etc.) and discussions by responding to questions accordingly	1.43	Beginning
Asks simple questions (who, what, where, when, why)	1.43	Beginning
Gives 1 to 2 steps directions	1.43	Beginning

Retells simple stories or narrates personal experiences	1.28	Beginning
Reading		
Identifies sounds of letters (using the alphabet of the Mother Tongue) The child can identify the following letter sounds: /a/b/c/d/e/f/g/h/i/j/k/l/m/n/o/p/q/r/s/t/u/v/w/x/y/z/)	1.87	Developing
Names uppercase and lowercase letters (using the alphabet of the Mother Tongue) (The child can name the following uppercase and lowercase letters: A B C D F G H I J K L M N O P Q R S T U V W X Y Z/a b c d e f g h i j k l m n o p q r s t u v w x y z	1.80	Developing
Matches uppercase and lowercase letters (using the alphabet of the Mother Tongue)	1.80	Developing
Identifies the beginning sound of a given word	1.45	Beginning
Distinguishes words that rhyme	2.27	Developing
Counts syllables in a given word	1.72	Developing
Identifies parts of the book (front and back, title, author, illustrator, etc.)	1.28	Beginning
Shows interest in reading by browsing through books, predicting what the story is all about, and demonstrating proper book-handling behavior (e.g., flipping pages sequentially, browses from left to right, etc.)	1.93	Developing
Interprets information from simple pictographs, maps, and other environmental prints.	1.44	Beginning
Writing		
Writes one's given name	2.11	Developing
Writes lower case and upper case letters	2.11	Developing
Express simple ideas through symbols (e.g., drawings, invented spelling)	2.41	Consistent
Total	1.78	Developing

In terms of speaking, the performance of the learners is displayed in Table 10-b. It is clearly shown that all begin with an overall mean of 1.41. It can be surmised that the learners are still beginning to perform the mentioned indicators in the table. As seen in the table the performance of the learners in terms of reading is indicated in Table 10-b.

Distinguished words that rhyme, show interest in reading by browsing through books, and identify sounds of letters using the alphabet of mother tongue received the highest means of 2.27, 1.93, and 1.87 respectively, and interpreted as developing. The lowest means of 1.28, 1.44, and 1.45 interpreted as developing are identifying parts of the book, interpreting information and identifying beginning sound of a given word. The performance of the learners in terms of writing is presented in Table 10-b. Expressing simple ideas through symbols is performed by the learners in the consistent stage while writing one's given name and writing lower case and upper case letters are performed developing stage. The overall mean is 1.78 or developing. At the very start of the school year, the majority, if not all the learners can write their names with correct spelling. However, it is done "rudely" meaning the correct form of the letters is not followed and are written beyond the lines of the pad paper. So that the teachers properly guide them. The learners told the teachers that they were taught by their parents or elder siblings. These were shared by the teachers to the writer of which the latter has similar observations in this regard.

3. Summary

Table 10-C
General Summary of the Performance of the Kindergarten Learners on the Developmental Domains

Seven Developmental Domains	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. Socio-Emotional and	2.06	Developing
2. Values Development	2.06	Developing
3. Understanding of the Physical and Natural Development	2.20	Developing
4. Mathematics	1.76	Developing
5. Physical Health and Motor Development	2.47	Consistent
6. Language Literacy and Communication	1.78	Developing
7. Aesthetic Development	1.91	Developing
Total	2.03	Developing

The general summary of the performance of the learners in the developmental domains is exposed in Table 10-C. It is revealed that the learners are consistent in performing physical health and motor development with a mean of 2.47. The means of understanding the physical and natural environment, 2.20, socio-emotional and values development, 2.06, aesthetic development, 1.91, language, literacy communication, 1.78 and mathematics, 1.76 are all in the developing stage. The overall weighted mean of 2.03 is interpreted as developing. Based from the Republic Act 10157 otherwise known as the Kindergarten Education Act of 2012 declares that it is the policy of the state to

provide equal opportunities for all children to avail of the accessible mandatory and compulsory kindergarten education that effectively promotes physical, social, intellectual, emotional and skills stimulation and values formation to sufficiently prepare them for formal elementary schooling.

3. Is there a significant difference in the performance of the Kindergarten learners in the seven developmental domains when grouped according to their profile?

a. age

Table 11
Results of Significant Difference in the Performance of the Kindergarten Pupils in the Seven Developmental Domains When Grouped According to Their Age

Pupils Age and Their Performance in the Following Developmental Domains	Mean		Significance of F	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
	5 years old	6 years old				
Socio-Emotional Development	2.31	2.64	0.0008	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Physical and Natural Environment	2.11	2.06	0.2199	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Values Development	2.44	2.23	0.0256	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Aesthetic Development	1.99	1.95	0.1942	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Mathematics	1.62	2.42	0.0001	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Physical Health and Motor Development	2.35	2.14	0.0179	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Language, Literacy, and Communication	1.83	2.15	0.0005	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 11 discloses the results of significant differences in the performance of the Kindergarten pupils in the Seven Developmental Domains when grouped according to their age. The results show that the P-values are less than 0.05 except for Physical and Natural Environment and Aesthetic Development. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is a significant difference in the performance of Kindergarten pupils in Socio-Emotional Development, Values Development, Mathematics, Physical Health, Motor Development, Language, Literacy, and Communication when grouped according to their age. It implies that the pupils when clustered by age differ from each other in their performance along these five domains. It further infers as indicated by their means in the table that the six-year-old pupils perform better in Social Studies, Mathematics, and Language, Literacy, and Communication.

Whereas, the five years are better in Values Development Physical Education, and Health. However, there is no significant difference in the performance of the Kindergarten pupils in Physical and Natural Environments, and Aesthetic Development when grouped by their age. It indicates that the five and six years old pupils are equally good in Science and Music Arts.

b. Sex

Table 12
Results of Significant Difference in the Performance of the Kindergarten Pupils in the Seven Developmental Domains When Grouped According to Their Sex

Pupils' Sex and Their Performance in the Following Developmental Domains	Mean		Significance of F	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
	5 years	6 years				
	male	female				
Socio-Emotional Development	2.21	2.61	0.0003	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Physical and Natural Environment	1.98	2.21	0.0005	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Values Development	2.31	2.45	0.0982	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Aesthetic Development	1.92	2.05	0.0377	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Not Significant
Mathematics	1.78	1.88	0.1867	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Significant
Physical Health and Motor Development	2.20	2.34	0.0230	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Language, Literacy, and Communication	1.83	2.00	0.0174	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant

The results of significant differences in the performance of the Kindergarten pupils in the Seven Developmental Domains, when grouped according to their sex, are disclosed in Table 12. It is revealed from the results that the P-values are less than 0.05 except for Values Development and Mathematics. This leads to the rejection of the Null hypothesis at a 0.05 significance level. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the performance of the Kindergarten pupils in Sociology-Emotional Development, Physical and Natural Environment, Aesthetic Development, Physical Health and Motor Development, and Language, Literacy, and Communication when grouped according to

sex. It means that the male and female pupils perform differently along the said five domains. It further notes as shown by their means that female pupils perform better in these domains than the male. On the other hand, there is no significant difference in the performance of the Kindergarten pupils in Values Development and Mathematics when grouped by sex. It states that both male and female pupils perform similarly in the aforementioned two domains.

c. Fathers' Educational Attainment

Table 13
Results of Significant Difference in the Performance of the Kindergarten Pupils in the Seven Developmental Domains When Grouped According to Fathers' Educational Attainment

Fathers' Educational Attainment and Pupil's Performance in the Following Developmental Domains	Mean						Significance of F	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
	College Grad	College Level	H. S Grad	H. S Level	Elem Grad	Elem Level				
Socio-Emotional Development	2.52	2.43	2.29	2.05	1.25	1.00	0.0007	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Physical and Natural Environment	2.41	2.44	2.62	2.17	1.50	1.50	0.0010	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Values Development	2.09	2.13	2.40	1.68	1.00	1.00	0.0005	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Aesthetic Development	2.52	2.59	2.69	2.32	1.50	1.50	0.0008	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Mathematics	2.41	2.15	2.62	2.17	1.50	1.50	0.0011	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Physical Health and Motor Development	2.52	2.54	2.69	2.32	1.50	1.50	0.0010	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant

Language, Literacy, and Communication	2.52	2.43	2.69	2.32	1.50	1.50	0.0009	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
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Table 13 displays the results of significant differences in the performance of the Kindergarten pupils in the seven developmental domains when grouped according to fathers' educational attainment. The results show that the P-values are less than 0.05. For this reason, the researcher rejects the null hypothesis at a five percent level of significance. As a result, there is a significant difference in the performance of the Kindergarten pupils in the seven developmental domains when grouped according to fathers' educational attainment. It manifests that the pupils vary in Their performance along the seven developmental domains mentioned in Table 14 when clustered by their fathers' educational qualifications. As indicated by the means, pupils whose fathers are high school graduates perform better in Values Development, Science, Music and Arts, Mathematics, Physical Education and Health, and Languages, Literacy, and Communication than the rest of the groups. Likewise, pupils whose fathers are college graduates perform well in Social Studies.

d. Mothers' Educational Attainment

Table 14
Results of Significant Difference in the Performance of the Kindergarten Pupils in the Seven Developmental Domains When Grouped According to Mothers' Educational Attainment

Mothers' Educational Attainment and Pupil's Performance in the Following Developmental Domains	Mean						Significance of F	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
	College Grad	College Level	H. S Grad	H. S. Level	Elem Grad	Elem Level				
Socio-Emotional Development	2.43	2.32	2.12	2.12	1.50	1.00	0.0026	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Physical and Natural	2.43	2.31	2.10	1.84	1.50	1.00	0.0015	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant

Environment										
Values Development	1.37	1.94	2.09	1.70	1.00	1.00	0.0037	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Aesthetic Development	2.40	2.29	2.19	2.19	2.00	2.00	0.0017	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Mathematics	2.43	2.50	2.16	1.98	2.00	1.00	0.0006	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Physical Health and Motor Development	2.37	2.63	2.20	2.02	2.00	2.00	0.0016	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Language, Literacy, and Communication	2.53	2.41	2.20	2.05	2.00	2.00	0.0764	P>0.05	Accept Ho	Not Significant

The results of significant differences in the performance of the Kindergarten pupils in the seven developmental domains, when grouped according to mothers' educational attainment, are displayed in Table 14. It is evident from the results that the P-values are less than 0.05 except for Language, Literacy, and Communication. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at a five percent significance level. Hence, there is a significant difference in the performance of the Kindergarten pupils in Socio-Emotional Development, Physical and Natural Environment, Values and Aesthetic Development, Mathematics, and Physical Health and Motor Development when grouped according to mothers' educational attainment. It implies that the pupils perform differently along the aforementioned domains when clustered by mothers' educational qualifications. As appended, the researcher further states that pupils whose mothers have finished college perform better in Social, Science, and Physical Education and Health. While, pupils with college undergraduate mothers do well in Music, and Arts, and Mathematics. Whereas, pupils whose mothers are high school graduates have better performance in Values Development. However, there is no significant difference in the performance of the Kindergarten pupils in Language, Literacy, and Communication when grouped according to mothers' educational attainment. It means that the pupils perform equally well in this domain when clustered by mothers' educational qualifications.

e. Fathers' Occupation

Table 15
Results of Significant Difference in the Performance of the Kindergarten Pupils in the Seven Developmental Domains When Grouped According to Fathers' Occupation

Fathers' Occupation and Pupils' Performance in the Following Developmental Domains	Mean					Significance of F	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
	Farmer	Government Employee	OFW	Private Employee	Self Employed Business Owners				
Socio-Emotional Development	2.41	2.08	1.82	2.40	2.43	0.0013	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Physical and Natural Environment	2.41	1.92	1.79	2.12	2.43	0.0008	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Values Development	2.41	1.77	1.59	1.96	2.43	0.0003	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Aesthetic Development	2.41	2.08	2.76	2.28	2.43	0.0007	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Mathematics	2.41	2.08	1.74	2.20	2.43	0.0005	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Physical Health and Motor Development	2.41	2.08	1.65	2.04	2.43	0.0004	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant

Language, Literacy, and Communication	2.53	2.23	1.53	2.16	2.43	0.0009	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
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Table 15 presents the results of significant differences in the performance of the Kindergarten pupils in the domains when grouped according to fathers' occupation. The results show that the P-values are less than 0.05. This signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the performance of the Kindergarten pupils in the seven developmental domains when grouped according to fathers' occupation. It indicates that the pupils vary in their performance in the seven developmental domains enumerated in Table 16 when clustered by fathers' work. The researcher further states, as appended, that pupils whose fathers are self-employed/business owners perform better in all the subjects than the rest of the groups.

f. Mothers' Occupation

Table 16
Results of Significant Difference in the Performance of the Kindergarten Pupils in the Seven Developmental Domains When Grouped According to Mothers' Occupation

Mothers' Occupation and Pupils Performance in the Following Developmental Domains	Mean					Significance of F	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
	Farmer	Government Employee	OFW	Private Employee	Self Employed Business Owners				
Socio-Emotional Development	2.41	2.13	1.80	2.43	2.43	0.0019	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Physical and Natural Environment	2.41	2.38	1.67	2.43	2.43	0.0016	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant

Values Development	2.41	1.38	1.07	2.07	2.43	0.0002	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Aesthetic Development	2.41	2.00	1.93	2.18	2.43	0.0008	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Mathematics	2.41	2.13	1.60	2.43	2.43	0.0014	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Physical Health and Motor Development	2.41	1.63	1.87	2.43	2.43	0.0015	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Language, Literacy and Communication	2.53	1.88	1.93	2.32	2.43	0.0022	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant

The results of significant difference in the performance of the Kindergarten pupils in the domains when grouped according to mothers' occupation are presented in Table 16. It is revealed from the results that the P-values are less than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is significant difference in the performance of the Kindergarten pupils in the seven developmental domains when grouped according to mothers' occupation. It implies that the Kindergarten learners vary in their performance in their Socio- Emotional Development, Physical and Natural Environment, Values Development, Aesthetic Development, and Language, Literacy and Communication when clustered by their mothers' work. The researcher further states that learners whose mothers' work is self-employed/business owners perform better in Social Studies, Music and Arts, and Mathematics. Whereas, pupils whose mothers' work is housekeeping are better in Science, Physical Educations, and Health, are Language, Literacy and Communication. While the learners whose mothers' are farmers have better performance in Values Development, and Physical Education and Health.

3. How do the teachers perform based on the classroom observation?

Table 17
Performance of Kindergarten Teachers

Teacher Performance	Mean	Interpretation	Effectiveness
A. Teacher Performance During Class Observation			
B. Performance Indicators			

1. Applies knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas.	6.00	Very Satisfactory	Effective
2. Uses a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills	5.60	Very Satisfactory	Effective
3. Applies a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills	5.89	Very Satisfactory	Effective
4. Manages classroom structure to engage learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environments	6.11	Outstanding	Very Effective
5. Manages learners' behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environments	6.40	Outstanding	Very Effective
6. Uses differentiated, developmentally-appropriate learning experiences to address learners' gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences	6.40	Outstanding	Very Effective
7. Plans, manages and implements developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts	6.89	Very Satisfactory	Effective
8. Selects, develop, and uses appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals	5.89	Very Satisfactory	Effective
9. Designs. select, organizes, and uses diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements.	6.56	Outstanding	Very Effective
Grand Mean	6.19	Very Satisfactory	Effective

Table 17 reveals that the teachers in the kinder level were performing very satisfactorily as indicated by the mean of 6.0 which also implies that the teachers were effective in the performance of their duties and responsibilities on the various areas of their respective discipline and they perform well in guiding the future leaders of the country. The data further shows that the teachers performed best in *using differentiated,*

developmentally-appropriate learning experiences to address learners' gender, needs, strengths, interests and experiences having garnered the highest performance rating of 6.89 which is equivalent to outstanding. Also rated as outstanding with a mean of 6.56, the teachers were assessed to be very effective in *selecting, developing, and using appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals* in their teaching job. Outstanding as well, with mean of 6.40, the teachers were rated very effective in *managing classroom structure to engage learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environments* as well as in *managing learners' behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environments*. The lowest rating the teachers received is about *application of knowledge of content within and across curriculum teaching areas* with a mean of 5.60 but still considered as satisfactory. Overall, with a grand mean of 6.19 or very satisfactory, the teachers were evaluated to be effective in the performance of their duties and responsibilities based from the performance indicators enumerated above.

5. is there a significant relationship between the performance of the Kindergarten learners on the seven developmental domains and their teachers' effectiveness?

Table 18
Results of Significant Relationship Between the Performance of the Kindergarten Learners on the Seven Developmental Domains and Their Teachers' Effectiveness.

Teachers' Effectiveness and Performance of the Kindergarten learners in the Following Developmental Domains	Computed Value of r	Significance of R	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Sociology-Emotional Development	0.7740	0.00073	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Physical and Natural Environment	0.7867	0.00071	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Values Development	0.7878	0.00070	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Aesthetic Development	0.7521	0.00075	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Mathematics	0.7716	0.00074	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Physical Health and Motor Development	0.7734	0.00073	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant
Language, Literacy and Communication	0.6525	0.00091	P<0.05	Reject Ho	Significant

Table 18 exhibits the results of significant relationship between the performance of the Kindergarten learners on the seven developmental domains and their teachers' effectiveness. The results show that the computed values of r indicate a positive high relationship since the values are large. However, the strength of the relationship has to be tested using the P-value. It is evident from the results that the P-values are less than 0.05. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis at a five percent significance level. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between the performance of Kindergarten learners in the seven developmental domains and their teachers' effectiveness. It manifests that the effectiveness of the teachers affects the performance of their learners in Socio-Emotional Development, Physical, and Natural Environment, Values Development, Aesthetic Development, Mathematics, Physical Health and Motor Development, and Language, Literacy, and Communication. It is further stated effective teachers produce well-performing learners.

7. What challenges do the teachers encounter in teaching kindergarten learners?

Table 19
Challenges Encountered by the Teachers

Challenges	Frequency	Rank
Too much paper work	9	1.5
Not enough time spent with the children	9	1.5
Difficulty of learners in paying attention for a significant period of time	7	3.5
Learners distracting the other children and monopolize much of teacher's time for discipline and attempts to regain the focus of the pupils or the class as a whole	7	3.5
Burden of helping to develop in preschoolers the foundation necessary for future academic success	6	5
Lack of interest of learners	5	6.5
Pay scale doesn't represent the dedication and hard work	5	6.5
Lack of Administrative support	4	8.5
Minimal Resources	4	8.5
Pupils Absenteeism	3	12
Not getting enough support from the parents	3	12
Difficulties in communicating with the parents	3	12

Not getting enough support from the parents	3	12
Varied Performance Levels of the pupils	3	12
Lack of instructional materials	2	15
Others, please specify	0	0

The challenges encountered by the teachers in teaching Kindergarten learners is disclosed in table 19. It is revealed that all the 9 teacher respondents claim too much paper work and not enough time spent with the children to be challenge they encounter in teaching Kindergarten learners. Difficulty of learners in paying attention for a significant period of time and learners distracting the other children received a frequency of 7 each or rank 3.5. Lack of instructional materials has the least frequency of 2 or rank 15. Too much paper works to be submitted is a phenomenon in the DepEd. It becomes worse because the authorities call for the immediate submission which at most times teachers have to comply and work on these even during class hours. The DepEd is giving although not sufficient instructional materials to be used by teachers in teaching Kindergarten learners. The insufficiency of the materials is being addressed by the schools particularly the teachers concerned. In fact, all teachers are required to make materials to support the delivery of every subject matter they teach.

Conclusions

The kindergarten learners meet the age requirement for their grade as prescribed by DepEd.

The kindergarten learners under study perform consistently in the developmental domains particularly in physical health, well-being and motor development, However, in terms of socio-emotional and values development, physical and natural environment, mathematics and language, literacy and communication, they are still at a developing stage.

The sex and age of the Kindergarten learners are important determinants in their performance in the developmental domains. The teachers' performance likewise significantly relates to the learners' performance in the developmental domains.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusions, the researcher recommends the following:

1. In as much as learners are still in the developing level in socio-emotional and values development, physical and natural environment, mathematics and language, literacy and communication, the teachers need to help them achieve a consistent level performance by being more aware of the learners interests' strengths and weakness so that appropriate methods, techniques and strategies can be done

2. Activities for the learners should be designed to be and engaging rather than stressful. fun doing such.
3. Differentiated activities should be provided to address the developmental needs of all learners. domains
4. Reduce the amount of paper work to allow teachers more time to interact with their pupils.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher made sure that during the conduct of the study, the following ethical concerns were followed to necessitate safe, anti-fraud, deliberate, and careful undertakings in the study:

1. The researcher, through proper communications, asked permission from the Division Office, and other concerned offices for the study;
2. The researcher also acknowledged the Department of Education and the Schools Division of the City of Ilagan for allowing her to conduct the study;
3. The researcher informed the respondents of the study through letters and a short orientation to the study. Data and information gathered were treated with utmost respect and confidentiality;
4. The researcher, properly cited gathered information and other relevant studies from authors, books, or any publications through proper citation.

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